

Rearing pink stem borer *Sesamia inferens* on the southwestern corn borer diet

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For 2 yr, we have successfully reared dark-headed stem borer *Chilo polychrysus*, armyworm *Mythimna separata*, cutworm *Spodoptera mauritia*, and pink stem borer on the southwestern corn borer diet. We studied the effect of that diet and a rice stem diet on the growth and development of the pink stem borer.

Rearing on rice stems. Seedlings of susceptible Rexoro were transplanted in 30-cm-diam clay pots. Fifty days after transplanting tillers were cut at the base. Stems were cut into 10-cm pieces and placed in 50 vials, each 11 cm long. To prevent the stem pieces from drying, a film of water was maintained at the base of each vial.

Pink stem borer moths emerging from field-collected pupae were allowed to oviposit on Rexoro plants inside cages. Egg masses were kept in a rearing room maintained at 28-30 °C and 70-80% relative humidity (RH), and allowed to hatch. Each stem piece in the vial was infested with two newly hatched pink borer larvae. Twice weekly the stem pieces were replaced with fresh ones. Individual weights of last-instar larvae and pupae were recorded. Emerging adults were allowed to oviposit on Rexoro plants and the incubation period of eggs was recorded.

Rearing on the southwestern corn borer diet. Field-collected pupae were caged and emerging moths were allowed to oviposit on Rexoro plants. Egg masses were incubated at 28-30 °C and 70-80% RH.

One litre of the custom southwestern corn borer diet (Bio-Mix #9763) was prepared using the following ingredients and steps:

<i>Pack A</i>	g/litre
Agar	17.2
<i>Pack B - dry mix</i>	
Wheat germ, toasted	21.1
Sucrose	25.0
Casein, vitamin-free	25.0
Salt mix Wesson	7.0
Linseed oil	0.2

Table 1. Duration of egg, larval, and pupal stages and length of life of adult pink stem borer reared on rice stems or southwestern corn borer diet.

Insect stage	Duration (d)			
	Rice stem		Artificial diet	
	Av	Range	Av	Range
Egg	7.6 ± 1.0	6-9	6.5 ± 1.1	5-8
Larva	28.9 ± 3.8	22-35	22.1 ± 5.9	18-33
Pupa	8.4 ± 1.1	7-10	10.6 ± 1.1	9-13
Adult	4.9 ± 0.9	3-6	3.3 ± 0.5	3-4

Table 2. Weights of last-instar larvae and pupae of pink stem borer when reared on rice stems or the southwestern corn borer diet.

Insect stage	Weight (mg)			
	Rice stem		Artificial diet	
	Av	Range	Av	Range
Larva	170.0 ± 46.5	112.1 - 279.6	217.3 ± 46.9	133.0 - 296.0
Pupa				
Female	164.7 ± 22.2	130.3 - 206.5	209.9 ± 38.8	163.6 - 278.0
Male	123.1 ± 20.6	92.0 - 183.9	148.2 ± 48.2	118.6 - 168.6

- Cholesterol 0.1
- Corn cob grits (autoclaved) 37.0
- Methylparaben 1.5
- Sorbic acid 0.5
- Pack C - vitamins*
- Vanderzant vitamin mix 5.3
- Ascorbic acid 2.1

1. Bring 545 ml of distilled water to a rolling boil.
2. Add 17.2 g of agar and stir until most of the agar has dissolved.
3. Pour water-agar mixture into the blender.
4. Add 118 g of pack B to the mixture and mix for 3 min at high speed.
5. Pour 366 ml of chilled distilled water into the blender and mix for 1 min.
6. Add 7.4 g of vitamins (pack C) and mix for 1 min.
7. Pour into rearing cups. If bacterial contamination is a problem, add with the vitamins 4 ml of 10% formaldehyde or 125 mg of aureomycin or both.

When the mixture cooled and the sides of the cup were dry, each cup was infested with two newly hatched pink stem borer larvae. Fifty cups were maintained for observation. Insect survival and growth duration of larvae and pupae were noted for each cup and individual weights were taken of last-instar larvae and pupae. The resulting moths were allowed to oviposit

on rice plants and incubation periods of the eggs taken.

Larval development was more rapid on the southwestern corn borer diet. The larval stage took 22 d versus 29 d for the rice stem diet (Table 1). The length of the egg and pupal stages were similar on the two food sources. Weights of last-instar larvae and pupae were distinctly higher on the southwestern corn borer diet, indicating that it is a better food source than rice stems (Table 2). □

Yellow stem borer (YSB) survival as affected by growth stage of early and medium-duration rices

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Previous studies have shown that IR46 is more resistant to the YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* at panicle initiation than at other growth stages. To determine the effect of growth stage on YSB survival from larva to adult, medium-duration IR46 was compared with early-maturing IR60. Survival was studied at early tillering, maximum tillering, panicle initiation, booting, and flowering.

Three seedlings were transplanted per clay pot on a staggered schedule so